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Raja Bhim Singh's Cenotaph by Rani Rambhavati: Multiple facets on reading a medieval inscription

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The historical landscape of Braj has been deeply enmeshed with Krishna worship also known as *Braj Mandal*, which spans across the present state of Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, and Rajasthan. The physical construction of *Braj Mandal* however is a medieval construct. Under the Mughals, the region developed as a center for various religious and cultural interactions. On the political front, imperial patronage in the form of land grants and contributions to temple building activities similarly became a major contributor to the flourishing of Braj.² These interactions led to the establishment of relationships that were imperative in popularizing the region of Braj as a pilgrimage center.

Vaishnavism had its outreach from the 16th century onwards when influential figures paid a visit to the region and popularised Krishna worship. The devotional sects founded by Chaitanya Mahaprabhu and Vallabha Acharya were imperative in spreading Krishna's devotion to far-flung areas. The western border of Braj encompasses a portion of present-day Rajasthan and hence the connection in devotional realms was forged and sealed uniquely. Among the Rajput states, the Kacchwaha rulers of Amber were the initiators of having had a strong presence in the region which they furthered by sponsoring several construction activities like that of the temple of Govindadev at Vrindavan, Haridev temple at Govardhan, and several others.³ Similarly, in the 18th century, the state of Bharatpur was carved out who had a portion of the *BrajChaurasi Kos* under them. These connections were nurtured over the centuries and specially at the time of Aurangzeb when several deities were taken out of Braj and ultimately found space in several Rajput principalities popularising *Krishna Bhakti* in the region.

Although it's a well-known belief that among the Mewar lineage Mirabai first to travel to Braj, the reference found are mostly oral narratives and hagiographical in nature. Mira's yatra to Vrindavan was contemporaneous to JivGoswami, one of the first six disciples of Chaitanya Mahaprabhu who were crucial in popularising Krishna bhakti and securing land grants from Mughal authorities for the construction of temple of GovindaDevaji and Madan Mohan.⁴ His uncle RupaGoswami however, is attributed for having found the first temple of GovindaDevaji which today lies only in ruins in the current temple premise. It can be observed that Mira may have seen this temple of GovindaDevaji perhaps in its initial humble form. Mira's visit can be seen as a connection to how Krishna bhakti gained popularity among the female devotees.

The inscription is a direct source of Rani Rambhavati's *BrajYatra*, as traveling was limited and pilgrim travels were also confined to a few. This inscription on the other hand is the first of its kind at least to say from Mewar's queen. Rambhavati was a widow and she did not perform sati. Which may or may not have been a very common sight given that her husband died on a battlefield. Despite this observation, the presence of inscription serves as an example that female devotees and especially widows were traveling to Braj for pilgrimage purposes. It can also be read as the first written inscription of a widow in Vrindavan itself.

Reading the inscription

The inscription is placed on a platform behind the temple and the *pradakshina path* of the temple of Govindadevji. The temple as it stands today was constructed in 1590 by Kacchwaha ruler Raja Man Singh. The temple has a history of its own which has been closely studied comprehensively by scholars.⁵ It was one of the most elaborate constructions of medieval times and was sanctioned by Akbar himself. It was later during the exodus of the 17th century in the reign of Aurangzeb where the temple was emptied and the *vigrah* (images of the deity) was taken out and later were housed at Jaipur.

संवत् १६९३ वरषे कार्तिक वदि ५ शुभदिने हजरत श्री श्री श्री साहे जहां राज्यै राणा श्री अ मर सिंघजी को बेटो र ज श्री भीम जी री राणी श्री रंभावती चौषडी सौराई छै ॥

“In the year *Sambat* 1693 (i.e., 1636 A. D.), on an auspicious day, KartikBadi 5, in the reign of the Emperor Shahjahan, this monument was erected by Rani Rambhavati, widow of Raja Bhim, the son of Rana Amar Sinh.” (translated by Growse, 1880:227).⁶

1. 1. कार्तिक संवत् 1693
2. कार्तिक वदी 5 शुभ दिने
3. हजरत श्री श्री श्री साहे
4. जहां राज्यै राणा श्री अ
5. मर सिंघजी को बेटो र
6. ज श्री भीम जी री राणी
7. श्री रंभावती चौषडी सौराई छै (जी)⁷

The inscription employs the usage of Nagari script with Rajasthani language. The first line reads as V. S. 1693 which when calculated comes down to 1636 A.D.⁸ The date mentioned here comes to the fifth day of *Krishna paksha* (or the fifth day from the new moon) in the auspicious month of *Kartik*.⁹ The next line is interesting as it mentions the name of the reigning Mughal ruler Shah Jahan. The word *Hazrat* is used against the popular usage of *Badshah*. In its precedence, the use of *Shri* three times indicates the admiration given

to the emperor. Usage of *nukta* (dot) is a diacritic mark under the letter ‘‘‘’ also showcases the skill of the inscriber and their knowledge of writing Persian words which was an uncommon sight in the inscriptions of that time period.

Another inscription found at the campus of GovindaDevji which predates this inscription writes about the construction of the temple.¹⁰ It mentions the name of Akbar as the reigning emperor during the construction of the temple, employs the word ‘*shaah*’ for him while another inscription on the Govinda dev *ashtak*¹¹ has used ‘*shriman*’ to pay respects to the reigning emperor. Such comparative analysis may indicate the subtlety of the choice of words employed to denote close relations between the Mughals and the ruler of Mewar. The inscription refers to Raja Bhim Singh as Amar Singh’s son, ‘सिंघ’ was a prevalent way of writing ‘सिंह’ on the other hand is a modern adaptation. Growse also transcribed it as *Sinh*. Amar Singh has been ascribed as ‘रण’ while Bhim Singh has been termed as ‘राजा’ which subtly indicates that while Amar Singh succeeded the throne his son did not.

In the last line, the word ‘चौषड़ी’ may appear as a colloquial way of writing the word ‘चौखंडी’.¹² What can be noted here is the usage of ‘ष’ for the alphabet ‘ख’, which was a prevalent way of writing even in the manuscripts of this time period and which is also indicative of the Rajasthani influence on BrajBhasha. However, what is unique in this inscription is the usage of both ‘ष’ and ‘ख’, like the first line of the inscription mentions the word ‘वरषै’. Hence, the letter ‘ष’ has been denoted for two letters.

A testimony to Mughal-Mewar relations

Ever since Mughal emperor Akbar absorbed the Rajput chiefs into the Mughal nobility a strong bond was initiated, this bond was further strengthened by matrimonial alliances. Such connections became viable during the succession of Jahangir when Raja Man Singh and Mirza Aziz Kokah fought in the tussle of succession between Jahangir and Prince Khusrao. Interventions like such were part of the large-scale diplomacy that ran into play. The perks of being attached to the cause of supporting a would-be emperor were immense and often rewarding.

In the year 1622, Prince Khurram rebelled against the imperial

forces of Jahangir. The Rajput chiefs who supported the cause of Khurram were Jagat Singh, Manrup, and Raja Bhim Sisodia of Mewar. In 1623 during the first encounter between the imperial forces and Shahjahan at Bilochpur in which the latter was defeated. However, Bhim Singh fought valiantly and was promoted to the rank of 5000/5000 with the title Maharaja bestowed upon him by the prince.¹³ He is said to have taken part in several battlefields. The text *Vir Vinod*¹⁴ has comprehensively described his campaigns against the imperial forces during that time. He fought actively for the cause and secured victory at the campaigns of Sepulchre, Bardwan and even succeeded in overcoming Patna. In October 1624 a battle was fought on the bank of river Tons against the imperial forces led by Jai Singh and Suraj Singh along with other eminent Rajput chiefs like Bhim Rathor, Prithvi Raj, Akhaya Raj, and Bir Singh Bundela. From Shahjahan's side, the forces were led by Raj Manrup and Raja Bhim along with Raja Bhim Singh's allies. Raja Bhim Singh Sisodia was killed in this battle by Gaj Singh. After the death of Jahangir, Shah Jahan sat on the throne in the year 1628 A. D. and strengthened the Mughal Mewar relations. An instance of Maharana Karan Singh and Prince Khurram exchanging *pagdiis* indicative of their close companionship.

On comparatively analyzing these data one can observe that the cenotaph was constructed in 1636 A. D., Prince Khurram revolted in 1622 A.D. and Raja Bhim Singh died fighting 1624 A.D. hence, the cenotaph was constructed after twelve years of the death of Raja Bhim Singh. Given the very nature of building cenotaphs, this information reflects that cenotaph appears as a memorial site against the belief of being a *pushpsamadhi*¹⁵ or containing the ashes of the Raja and therefore, an indicator that Rani Rambhavati traveled to the region of Braj. Furthermore, the inscription does not mention the contemporaneous ruler of Mewar which can be another indicator that the cost of the construction may have been borne from Rani's expenditure and was not state-sponsored.

Re-construction and preservation

The cenotaph was originally placed either at the front entrance of the temple or at a distance but, well within the circumference of the temple's premise. Growse mentions it to be located "on the south side of the choir stood a large domed and pillared *chhatrif* of very handsome and harmonious design, though erected 40 years later than the

temple.”¹⁶ Another reference on the location of *chhatri* was painted by Sitaram in 1815. The painting depicts the location a little far yet within the premise of the GovindaDevji temple. The artist has also shown the dilapidated condition of the *chhatri* which Growse describes in 1817 as being “in a very ruinous condition”. The painting, however, depicts the temple to be in utmost ruins and having no roof which appears to differ a little from the description Growse provides two years later. Nonetheless, it does provide evidence of the cenotaph to be located within the premises of the temple.

It was through the intervention of Mathura’s district collector Growse that this monumental task of reconstruction of the temple of Govinda dev was completed. The temple was in a dilapidated state and only under his personal supervision, the task of its preservation was managed well. Mathura’s memoir also mentions that the *garbhgrih* had fallen completely and to structurally secure the temple he constructed a wall and placed the *chhatri* behind it.

“As the monument was in a very ruinous condition and had been rendered still more insecure by reducing the level of the ground around its foundations, it was taken down and re-erected on the platform that marks the site of the old sacrarium, where it serves to conceal the bare rubble wall that rises behind it.” (Growse 1883) Hence, the cenotaph’s present location was re-constructed where it now stands as a precious little piece of history.

Conclusion

Unlike, documents, which were often intended for archival storage and had limited accessibility to the population, a construction activity so to say was one way of the ruler’s presence among the public. Even a small construction like that of a cenotaph was there to remain in public sight. The appearance of a woman’s name on an inscription perfectly preserved over the years recognizes their presence as sponsors of construction activity. Such small pieces of history provide for multiple dimensions on not just the prevailing socio-political scenario but, also serve as connecting dots in the larger historical narratives.

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- ³ See Entwistle, A. W. *Centre of Krishna Pilgrimage*, Groningen: Egbert Forsten, 1987.
- ⁴ Habib, Irfan and Mukherjee, BrajBhum in *Mughal Times: The State, Peasants and Gosains*, Delhi: Primus Books, 2020, p. 59.
- ⁵ See Hortsman, Monika, *In Favour of Govinddevji: Documents Relating to a Deity of Vrindaban and Eastern Rajsthan*, New Delhi: Manohar Publications, 1999 and Case, Margaret H. (ed.) *Govindadeva: A Dialogue in stone*, New Delhi: IGNC, 2002.
- ⁶ Growse, F. S. *Mathura: A District Memoir*, 1883.
- ⁷ Sharma, Rajesh, ब्रज के शिलालेख, Vrindavan: BrajSanskirtiShodhSansthan, 2014.
- ⁸ There is a misprinting in F. S. Growse's *Mathura Memoir*; it has written the date to be 1836 A. D. while the actual date calculated is 1636 A.D.
- ⁹ The month of Kartik is an exclusive time for traveling to Braj, it is also a well-known time for the BrajChaurasi KosYatra and remains a popular pilgrimage time even at present.
- ¹⁰ *Ibid.*, pp 4-5.
- ¹¹ *Ibid*
- ¹² चौखड़ी can be defined as having चार दर where दर means दरवाजा or door.
- ¹³ Zaidi, S. Inayat A. "The Rajput Chiefs and Prince Shahjahan's Revolt: Consequences," *Islamic Culture* 6I, no. 4, 1987, p 66.
- ¹⁴ Das, Shyamal, *Vir Vinod*, vol. II, 1886, pp- 286-289.
- ¹⁵ Pushp Samadhi has a long history of people securing the ashes and constructing a samadhi over them. It was done to pay respect to the people who were important religious dignitaries. Braj houses several such small and big samadhi which has a long history of their own.
- ¹⁶ Growse, *ibid.*, p.247.